

Seedling News

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MARCH 1991

Speedy Tea

Warrick Nelson

Clonal tea propagation traditionally takes some eighteen months from cutting to transplanting. Utilizing the **Speedling** system can reduce this time by half.

Southern Natal tea growers starting their tea plantations from scratch were faced with the long waiting period from deciding to grow tea to actually having tea in the ground. Ron Rossler began growing tea cuttings in the traditional manner, but soon decided to try adapting tea propagation into his **Speedling** style of seedling nursery. The success of this experiment over the last three years has meant that Ron is now propagating a high percentage of the tea still required for this new venture.

The similarity in principle between clonal tea propagation and clonal timber propagation is striking. The cuttings are stuck directly into the trays from which they will be transplanted some nine months later. Rooting takes place on sand beds with misting. This operation ensures that adequate moisture is available to prevent desiccation, while excess water in the plugs is readily drained away by the sand.

Cuttings are checked regularly for

rooting since it is undesirable to leave the cuttings in the rooting area too long. **Kompel Seedling Growing Medium** is used for rooting because of its high air filled porosity and rapid draining. Model 98 or 72 **Speedling** trays treated with **Styrodip** are used. The **Styrodip** prevents the vigorous adventitious roots from growing into the trays as well as helping to develop a fine, fibrous root system.

As soon as rooting has occurred, the cuttings are transferred to the growing-on tables. Here normal seedling irrigation is applied with a hydroponic nutrient solution added to the water. Shoot growth is stimulated and further root growth to fill the root plug is encouraged.

Cuttings could be transplanted much earlier than they are, but the strong winds often experienced in this region demand a more robust plant. It has also been found that weed control is easier and more effective where larger plants are transplanted.

Transplanting into the deep sandy soils is easily done, care being taken not to plant too deeply and not to damage the root system. Tea is a long-term crop, with some plantations still productive

Healthy root development on this tea cutting shortly after moving into the growing-on area. Vigorous new leaves are now being developed. The dark green colouring develops later.

after a hundred years. Extra care to prevent root damage is therefore of vital importance. Inefficient roots can reduce the vigour of the plant for its entire life.

Approaching clonal propagation from the point of view of the principles involved has paid off handsomely in this venture. Not only is the new nursery system more efficient in terms of time, it also produces more vigorous transplants easier to handle in a much smaller nursery. ▼

Tea cuttings on the rooting beds. Note the temporary shade cloth cover over recently stuck cuttings.

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New Pansy Releases

Peter Kruger

The new **Maxim Marina** Pansy – a 1991 All America Selections winner.

There are a few outstanding new hybrid Pansies due to be released by Kudu Seed this Autumn. Starke Ayres is

planning a number of promotions, so bedding-plant growers are advised to purchase seed in time to have plants

available. Check with your seed representative for details of promotions. These new hybrid Pansies are going to be featured widely in the print media and are also due to be used in the television Gardening programme on G.M.S.A.

Probably the most important new releases are the two new additions to the enormously successful **Maxim** Pansy range. **Maxim**, which are medium-sized, faced Pansies, have endeared themselves to the gardening public of South Africa and are regarded as the best value for money when it comes to continuous flowering throughout the cooler months of the year. **Maxim Marina** is the first Pansy to be awarded an All American Selection award for a bedding plant. The flowers are light blue with a darker blue face. **Maxim Sunset (Love)** is a unique new colour with golden yellow petals and a bronzy-red blotch.

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Pansy **Padparadja** – named after a rare stone from Sri Lanka because of its similar colour intensity.

Editor's View

I am frequently contacted by seedling nurserymen asking whether I know anybody who would be able to manage a seedling nursery. I am very seldom able to offer any advice.

Virtually all businesses which rely on technically-trained staff have to ensure an adequate educational infrastructure. With an adequate basic technical training, skills required for the specific nursery jobs will be easily learned, and with a minimum of costly mistakes. Technikons offering horticultural courses need to include aspects pertinent to a seedling nursery. Unless seedling growers bring this need to their attention, the serious shortage of

trained job-applicants will continue indefinitely.

Without a strong technically-oriented background, it is virtually impossible to remain objective when problems in the nursery arise. The problems associated with growing wattle seedlings this summer are an example. I am involved on a consultative basis with many nurserymen, and problems in nurseries are typically blamed on either the seed or the growing medium. Weather conditions, correct watering and fertilization, disease and pests, herbicide contamination of chemical sprays are some of the factors to consider. By the time the seedlings show a problem, the cause of the problem is no longer apparent. Careful piecing-together of what is known about all of the possible factors may achieve a more accurate diagnosis. Few problems are solved without knowing their cause. Blind blame might feel good but does nothing when the same problem next arises.

Most seedling growers take great care to produce a top-quality seedling. The apparent lack of interest on the part of the purchaser in the quality of these seedlings is strange. There is considerable evidence to guide farmers and foresters as to the consequences of forcing the nurseryman to hold seedlings beyond their prime. Why risk

your investment by not planning adequately to use seedlings when they are ready? Summer cabbages delayed in the nursery a mere two weeks may result in a yield-potential reduction of some twenty percent, while with cauliflowers the reduction may be as much as fifty percent.

Bedding-plant growers and their retail associates need to take a long, hard look at the quality of seedlings sold to gardeners. I have seen Zinnia seedlings in a twelve-pack varying in height from four to eighteen centimetres, Lobelias so weak they had no option but to die, and cauliflowers complete with mature curds. Once bitten, twice shy is the unfortunate result, to the detriment of those who do a good job. ▼

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Medium won't wet?

Most nurserymen in South Africa are using an organic growing medium. A characteristic of these products is that when their moisture content drops below about 15% they become very difficult to re-wet. A suitable wetting agent added to the water is necessary to overcome this problem. At a pinch, even a few drops of dish-washing liquid can be used, but be careful as some may have an herbicidal effect! ▼

Tangled Tree Roots

Janine Kietzka

Institute for Commercial Forestry Research

A trial of *Eucalyptus grandis* seedlings grown in four different nursery containers has shown some interesting root formations after nine months in the field. Although no overall tree growth differences have been noted yet, some of the treatments showed root distortions and potential points of instability.

Four different types of trays were used. Seedlings grown in Speedling model 98 and 128 trays with Styrodip treatment, the Unigro tubes and the SAPPI Mark I model 49 trays were compared. In addition to the tray comparisons, seedlings were nine, thirteen or twenty-one weeks old when transplanted.

Root form was noticeably different for seedlings from the different containers. Early growth of the Unigro and SAPPI seedlings showed a 'root cage' structure. The degree of distortion in these trays was more pronounced in the older seedlings. After nine months in the field the 'root cage' showed as a swollen knob at the base of the trunk. The development of a tap root was frequently inhibited or severely constricted. Seedlings grown in the polystyrene trays treated with Styrodip showed no 'root cage' effect but in some cases also showed tap root distortions or inhibition.

After nine months growth in the field there was little or no difference in the

The knob of roots formed at the base of the trunk. Adventitious lateral roots sometimes grow from above the root collar. A lack of tap root growth is quite common.

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Seedling News

The cost of duplication of articles in English and Afrikaans is prohibitive. However, any readers requiring a specific article translated are welcome to request a typescript copy. Please include a self-addressed stamped envelope with your request and specify the desired article clearly.

Die kostes verbonde aan die plasing van artikels in beide Engels en Afrikaans is ontsaglik duur. Lesers wat 'n vertaling van enige artikel benodig is egter welkom om daarvoor aan te vra. Stuur 'n self-gedresseerde koevert met die nodige posseël aan ons en dui duidelik aan watter artikel u benodig. ▼

The interior of the knob of roots showing the growing medium trapped inside and the severe distortion possible in these root systems.

size of the trees, despite varying seedling sizes at time of transplanting. These results confirm observations from similar Canadian trials, that even severe root distortions may have little

effect on early tree height or stem diameter growth. Longer-term trials are required to determine the effects of various root forms on older trees. ▼

SGASA news

The annual get-together of members of the Seedling Growers' Association is a valuable experience. It is an opportunity to meet others in the industry, to see new products on offer by suppliers and to hear the results of sponsored research projects. This year, the symposium will be in the Transvaal during May. It will be good to see a full representation of Transvaal nursery

members.

Labour relations in the seedling industry are of considerable importance considering the labour-intensive nature of growing seedlings. This is the topic for the keynote address of the Symposium. Other speakers will focus on more technical nursery aspects including tray sterilization, seedling nutrition, nursery diseases and their

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Hybrid asparagus takes over

The South African asparagus industry is growing rapidly because of an increased demand for top-quality asparagus on foreign markets. The 1990 season saw a substantial increase in asparagus plantings. This trend is expected to continue during this season.

All-male hybrids of asparagus were used in most of the new plantings last year. The advantages of these all-male hybrids are higher yields of top-quality spears; come into commercial production sooner; regenerate new spears quicker after each pick; have superior vigour; display improved drought tolerance; and have a longer commercially viable lifespan. The most popular cultivar at present is **UC 157 F₁**.

Establishing asparagus is a long-term project. Seed quality is therefore of cardinal importance. The extra cost of seed from a reputable source must be seen in the context of the crop. One kilogram of seed is sufficient to establish two hectares using transplants. Quality seed may cost R1 000 per kilogram more than cheaper sources. This represents an extra outlay of less than R100 per hectare per year over the commercial life of the plants. This is a very small premium to pay on a long-term, high-value crop like asparagus, particularly when it may

Asparagus seedlings grown in Speedling trays. The root plugs have been washed out to show the healthy root growth. Model 98 trays are generally preferred for asparagus seedlings.

mean the difference between success and failure.

Planning ahead is essential for growing asparagus. Seed is in short

supply and growers should order their seed now for sowing in 1992 if they wish to be certain of obtaining the best quality seed. ▼

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SNIPPETS

Better tomatoes

Charging the seedling root plug with nutrients just before transplanting is a fairly common technique in South Africa. The extra nutrients, particularly nitrogen, support the plant and encourage rapid establishment after transplanting. This technique replaced the 'hungry seedling' concept some years ago.

Trials on tomato transplants reported last year confirm that seedlings suffering a temporary nutrient shortage just before transplanting showed

reduced shoot growth and lower yields. Seedlings grown with lower nutrient levels throughout tended to produce the best yields, while high nutrient levels showed rapid shoot growth, but not the best yields. Growing a harder seedling by maintaining relatively low nutrient levels during nursery growth, with a good nutrient charge just before transplanting, should therefore offer the best transplant recovery-rate and the highest yield potential. ▼

Transplanting tips

Always transplant seedlings with the root plug saturated. The reason for this is that water tends to be sucked out from a coarse medium (the root plug) to a fine medium (the surrounding soil). If the plug is not wet before transplanting, the seedling is unlikely to grow vigorously and may even die.

Seedlings should be transplanted with the surface of the root plug just below ground level. This will prevent the top of the plug drying out in the sun and drawing moisture out of the rest of the plug.

Puddle-planting is fairly commonly understood in forestry circles. It entails applying water into the transplanting hole either just before transplanting, or just after placing the seedling to settle the soil. Foresters, in particular, should consider puddle-planting even in drizzly conditions because of the generally reduced rate of seedling loss with this technique. Other users of seedlings can generally apply irrigation straight after transplanting. Many transplanting machines use the same principle by directing a jet of water around the seedling to settle the soil. ▼

Why transplant?

Recent lettuce trials in Texas and Florida have confirmed common observations that seedling establishment can produce a more uniform stand than direct sowing. These regions have problems with hot, dry soils for late summer and autumn lettuce establishment. Thermo-dormancy in lettuce is a common problem when soil/medium temperatures rise above

25°C. This results in erratic seedling emergence, often associated with low vigour. Marketable yields under these conditions were improved by 42 percent with only two harvests necessary to harvest 80 percent of the harvestable heads. Very similar soil temperatures exist in South Africa over the same time. ▼

At the dawn of new challenges for the seedling industry

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TUNNEL TALK

Meran tomatoes

Meran F₁ hybrid is an intermediate type, medium-early variety with medium vigour. As the leaves are smallish and open, good fruit set is possible even under poor light conditions. The plants are resistant to TMV, Verticillium and

Fusarium race 1. **Meran** can be grown in greenhouses, plastic tunnels and outdoors.

High levels of potassium have been found to improve fruit colouring and transport quality.

Preliminary results of trials conducted in conjunction with the Association of Vegetables Under Protection (AVUP) in Stellenbosch have shown that the new **Starke Ayres** introduction **Meran** outyields the current standard and has a higher percentage of large fruits.

Cucumber water use

Warrick Nelson

Cucumbers in South Africa appear to survive on remarkably little water. Dutch literature suggests that their mature plants transpire five or more litres of water per day. Local plants appear to be able to survive on less than two litres per day, including the water which drains out!

A combination of high humidity, low water temperature and too-infrequent water applications are probably the reason for this marked difference in water usage. If the relative humidity is too high (above 75%), the ability of the plant to use water to control leaf temperature and to use water to move nutrients within itself will be reduced. Typical results are large, soft leaves susceptible to disease, thickened stems, abortion of young fruits, curved fruits with poor shelf-life and general symptoms of nutrient deficiency.

Irrigation scheduling varies tremendously between growers. Some apply water twice per day, others far more often. Most use a time or 'wilt index' approach, although light integrators have been introduced. As the diagram shows, water requirements during night time may not be met by normal methods of irrigation scheduling. Drought during night time may have further consequences, since calcium and boron are usually only transported to young growing tips when plants are fully turgid.

When irrigation is controlled by light integrator, all the water is supplied during daylight (a). With a direct medium sensor (b), it can be seen that the crop is demanding water during darkness too. Boron and calcium tend to be only transported to fruits and growing tips at night when plants are turgid.

TUNNEL TALK

Conductivity

Warrick Nelson

Monitoring the level of nutrients applied to seedlings and tunnel plants is of vital importance to their health. The most common (and convenient) means is to use a conductivity meter. However, unless the concept of conductivity is understood, the meter reading can be either meaningless or misleading.

Conductivity is a measure of the amount of electricity conducted by a solution and is thus opposite in meaning to electrical resistance. To measure conductivity, two electrodes are placed into the solution to be measured, an electrical charge is applied and the amount of electricity passing through the solution is measured. Commercial conductivity meters do this.

Notice that this description of conductivity makes no mention of fertilizers at all. Conductivity is not a measure of concentration in fertilizer solutions. However, the concentration of a specific fertilizer mixture can be **checked** by using a conductivity meter. For this reason, the conductivity of certain fertilizer mixtures at specific

concentrations is usually mentioned in the directions for that fertilizer.

All fertilizer solutions contain dissolved salts. It is these salts which conduct electricity. The conductivity of the solution is therefore linked to the concentration of salts present in solution. The more salts, the higher the conductivity. It is this link which makes conductivity very useful to monitor fertilizer concentrations.

Only molecules with a charge affect conductivity. Urea is an important source of nitrogen in fertigation, but it does not form charged particles in solution. It is therefore not reflected in conductivity measurements.

Since conductivity is not a measure of fertilizer content or concentration, it is meaningless to refer to an "optimum conductivity" without specifying the fertilizer mixture and water quality. This means that a calibration curve is necessary for each nursery and the specific fertilizer used. For example, in the graph it is easily seen that the same conductivity reading is caused by different concentrations of the two

fertilizers. This is possible even if the nutrient content of the fertilizers is the same. If the content of nutrients is the same for these two fertilizer mixtures, applying them at the same conductivity reading will result in very different levels of nutrient being applied to the plants. ▼

Chemicult in pure water at normal working strength will result in a conductivity reading of 2 mS/cm. If the nutrient injector system is based on supplying this nutrient, changing to another fertilizer means that the entire fertigation system must be checked and recalibrated. In this example, applying the alternate fertilizer to give irrigation water with the same conductivity reading would result in double the nutrients actually being applied.

Pythium in cucumbers —

extracted and translated from "TUINDERIJ"
by Wim van der Arend and Allan MacKinley

Pythium is a 'weakness parasite' unable to attack active, healthy tissue. It lives off dead and dying tissue.

There are three factors which influence a *Pythium* attack. The health status of the plant, the environment of the plant and the presence or absence of the parasite. If the parasite is not present, even susceptible plants will not get sick.

To prevent *Pythium*, we need to pay attention to the quality of the plant, the growing conditions and hygiene.

Whilst raising the plant, root temperatures should not be allowed to get too high. Root temperatures can be raised by high floor temperatures when heating from below and by direct radiation from the sun. Large leaves on the plants give more shade and hence reduce root temperatures. The electrical conductivity (EC) and the method of watering are also important. Fluctuations in the EC and in the temperature of the irrigation water should be prevented. It is better not to give water from the top.

Each time a plant is disturbed, so is its

growth. This can result in weaker plants and in consequence a *Pythium* attack. Measures to minimize the lifting, transporting, storing and transplanting of plants should be implemented.

The entire transplanting operation must be carefully planned in order to minimize the disturbance and interruption of growth of the plants. Transplanting in the evening minimizes the growth check.

The time between lifting plants and transplanting should be as short as possible. If the plants have to be stored after lifting, then they should be placed into storage immediately after lifting and stored at a temperature of 19 °C. Strong plants should be adequately supported so that they cannot bend. The plants should be tied immediately after transplanting, so the strings should be in position before transplanting.

During transplanting, short irrigations should be given periodically to keep all the bags moist, not only after all the plants have been transplanted. Frequent irrigations are necessary until

the roots have grown into the growing medium in the bag. The drip-water should not touch the stem when irrigating. Over-irrigation should be avoided, as roots standing in water are deprived of oxygen. This causes them to weaken and they are then susceptible to parasite attack. The supply of oxygen to the roots should be optimal at all times.

After transplanting, regrowth can be aided by reducing evaporation. This can be achieved by roof-raining, screening or whitewashing. These measures should only be used in moderation as they may result in the growing points being burned if the plants are too soft.

If *Pythium* should occur despite attempts to restrict it, remove the dripper from the attacked plant's bag. The growing medium will dry out and retard the development of the fungus, and at the same time the oxygen status of the medium will improve, allowing the roots to recover. When chemical control is used, drenching is more effective than applications via drip irrigation. ▼

When Poppa needs a boss

Symond Fiske, Editor of *Effective Farming* and Director of Agri-Africa

Farming was a Poppa and Momma business when Poppa and Momma were kids. If the business failed, the farm was sold and another Poppa and Momma took over. If it flourished it was divided into an appropriate number of new Poppa and Momma businesses when the next generation took over.

But such are the economics of scale these days that Poppa and Momma can seldom expect to compete any longer with a stand-alone concern. It still works with dairying, it is true, and with small stock in the Karoo. But horticulture (especially), most kinds of intensive crop farming and the beef business are all sliding into different hands. The survivors now are the big guys, and the part-timers.

The part-timers tend to live on their wits and have a lot of fun while eking out a precarious income by catering for niche markets too small to interest the establishment. A supplementary cash flow from something more boring and lucrative than farming often helps. They come and go. Their farm businesses seldom last more than a decade... unless, that is, they stumble upon a winning idea. Then they may join the big guys. Such ventures, if they succeed, seldom pause for long at the Poppa and Momma size any more.

S. Fiske

Farmers know this. It is rarely considered sensible, these days, to fragment a farm business for inheritance.

Hence the new breed of large family farm: awkwardly (and often acrimoniously) managed by an

extended family of brothers, uncles, nephews, grandparents, largely for the benefit of sisters, cousins and aunts.

Managing a business with a team selected on what is euphemistically known as 'the lucky sperm principle' is tough enough. Keeping the team in harmony can be equally difficult.

The solution often lies outside the family. Once it has been acknowledged that the family hasn't bred (and can't be expected to breed) all the talents needed to manage and expand a big competitive high-tech business, it is a small step to call in professional help. Substantial family businesses have been doing that for years.

What is new is that an increasing number are demanding that at least one of the professional advisers joins the Board. Apart from obliging the accountant, lawyer or business management consultant to take a more active and intimate interest in the results of the advice he gives, this has the cardinal virtue of bringing some discipline to family board meetings. Senior management within the family suddenly becomes more focused when it has a proper board to report to and a proper board from which it must obtain permission before embarking on any major investments or diversifications. ▼

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New Seed Products Update

Early Gold, a new extra-early onion, has proven to be up to ten days earlier than other early varieties. This gives growers the chance to catch the high-priced early market.

The golden brown bulbs are deep flat to flask shaped and have excellent quality even after three months storage. The plants have shown good tolerance to downy mildew and bolting percentages have been minimal.

Indra sweet pepper for tunnel or field production is a high-yielding early blocky type, colouring from dark green to deep red. The fruits are firm, thick-walled with three to four lobes, and a mean mass of 150g. Their appearance and quality are outstanding at either green or red stage. The plants have a large compact frame with resistance to TMV (physio 0) and tolerance to Cucumber Mosaic Virus.

Orobelle sweet pepper is another high-yielding, early blocky type for tunnel or field production. The fruits are firm, thick-walled with three to four lobes, and colour from green to yellow. The ripe yellow fruits have excellent quality and outstanding appearance. The plants have a large compact frame with resistance to TMV (physio 0) and tolerance to Potato Virus Y and Stip.

Jupiter (seedless) watermelon has round, very dark green fruit with bright crimson flesh. The texture is excellent with good flavour (sugar content 15° Brix). Fruit mass of three to six kilograms and ability to transport well make this cultivar ideal for both local and export markets. The vine is tolerant to downy mildew and in trials remained healthy when most other varieties had succumbed to leaf diseases.

It is necessary to plant about 30% of pollinator plants. The pollinator should be chosen to have fruits easily distinguishable from **Jupiter**. Seedling growers need to take care to supply the specific requirements for germinating seed of seedless watermelon hybrids.

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BALOO – NEW

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